

THE RANGE OF TOPICS IN THE POET'S POETRY

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Abstract. This article is written by Mirzohid Botir, one of the talented artists with his own voice and style in Uzbek literature, published in the poetry collection "Eng yorug' xat", "Yozug'im-Allohning eng yorug' xati", "Axir salovatdir shoir yig'lasa!", "Oydan yuzing izladim", "Tunab qolur ko'zlarimga tun", "Yig'ladim men, onam-a!", "Baxtsizlarni kechir, Xudoyim!", "Yelkansiz kema", "Ibodot fasli", "Hasadgo'yning ko'karmas bog'i", "Xudoga maktub", "Tik turib o'larkan datraxtlar!" in the example of poems like.

Key words: Beautiful poems, charming ghazals, the language of the poem, poet's psyche, poets' soul singer, interpreter of the heart, symbol of the night, pride, sincere image of the heart, scope of topics.

INTRODUCTION

The collection of poems "Eng yorug' xat" written by Mirzohid Botir (Mirzohid Botirov), who has his own voice and style in Uzbek literature, attracts attention with its artistic strength and variety of themes. It is known that Mirzahid Batir wrote more social life scenes in his poems with beautiful words that are the gift of the heart, and in this poetic bouquet, Motherland, mother, poet, word, love, happiness, visal, hijran, night, morning, life, world, heart, etc. I think it is permissible to admit that it is a collection of beautiful poems on various topics. It would not be an exaggeration to say that his poetry collections "Hayrat chohlari", "Derazangni och", "Hayot simfoniyasi" are proof of our opinion.

As you wander through the bosom of creativity of a promising artist, you will witness how his beautiful poems and charming ghazals, which he writes with the intention of achieving the status of a true poet, will involuntarily cheer the heart. Following Mirzahid's work, the following words of the literary scholar, Hero of Uzbekistan Ozad Sharafiddinov come to mind: "Poets are born in different ways. There are poets, like a baby learning to walk, he learns the alphabet of poetry for many years, he tries to follow different poets, he searches and finds his way, even though he struggles with it more and more. There are poets, the first from the very beginning, they amaze everyone, turn their emotions, feelings, and thoughts into unfamiliar images, and begin to sing in "words undreamed of by legends". It is difficult to fit them into the concept of "young poets". In fact, if you directly observe Mirzohid Botirov's work, you will be sure how correct this opinion is. When you read the poet's poems, you can feel the influence of the poetry of the People's Poet of Uzbekistan Muhammad Yusuf. The fact that the poet's poetry has features related to folkliness, sincerity, clarity, and reflection in bright colors confirms how correct our opinion is.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

When it comes to the issue of the poet's skills, we think it would be appropriate to pay attention to the conversation between the poet and the editor-in-chief of the newspaper, T.

Mustafоеv, which was recently published in the September 30, 2022 issue of the "Termiz University" newspaper called "Surkhan is a second country for me."... Famous One of our writers spoke about you and said, "Mirzahid found the language of the poem. I don't know whether it will be the language of the poem or not? How to find its language?"

- Very nice question (laughs). But I don't know which writer said it, but I can't say that I found the language of the poem. There is pain in my words, what comes out with pain will surely sink in with pain. I can't copy and write something. When I see a blind person, when I see a disabled person, when I see an orphan, and the burden of his pain is transferred to me, only after that something that shakes the heart is poured on paper."

When the time comes, the truth about a person's name also has an effect on his creativity. The word Mirzahid consists of a compound word, mir is a shortened form of the Arabic word amir, the title of ruler, ruler, prophet's descendants, and zahid is an Arabic word that means a person who is patient, pious, and renounces the world. It seems that we can come to the conclusion that the way a person lives depends on the name given to a person. If you observe the poet's poetry, you will see a series of inscriptions in almost many of his poems, which refer to grief, pain, suffering, and dreams. In our opinion, the main reason for this is that the poet went through the difficult and trying days of his life several times. But one thing is that when a person leans on the Truth in painful moments, he writes his brightest wishes in the kingdom of the heart to the Truth. The poet, who could not find a sincere and honest, pure heart in the midst of the world's ravages, was telling his beautiful letter to God, which is the product of his bright feelings. In the collection of "Eng yorug' xat ", which contains elegant poems from the flowerbed of our hearts, with unique expressions that do not spill out, the poem called "Yozug'im-Allohning eng yorug' xati"

The stones are cracked
I'm in a secret
My eyes are not enough
I am in the light
I am in a heart closed to the world,
Fate-
The brightest letter of God, says the poet.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The poem was actually written on the 53rd anniversary of Zahiriddin Muhammad Muhammad Babur, the day after Alisher Navoi, the Uzbek classical poet, but if we fully research the content of the poem, the wanderlust created by Babur is in the poet's life. It is as if he has found his own justification, he has found his own justification, and his sufferings and lamentations from the Motherland, which he committed suicide, are also concentrated. Even if he lives in such a state, it can be felt that he has the confidence to see even the brightest days that God has written on his forehead. It is not for nothing that the poet said "Fate is the brightest letter of Allah". If we go deeper into the work of the poet, you will see in the poem a sincere soul, a lover of spiritual freedom, who considers creativity to be his destiny, and who takes part in the poem with a good heart. In the poet's poetry, the image of the poet has different forms. In particular, a clock is prominent in his poems. When you read Kungil's poem, the strictness and sincerity of the description of feelings in the poet's couplet attract and amaze you:

... Sometimes a stone, sometimes a flower, telling a secret,

Thinking of someone in pain
Making the world cry with words
Maybe it's a sign if the poet cries?!

Or

The poet comes to the world to cry.
Some secret pain comes to the fore,
Pen and paper come to sharpen,
After all, it is a blessing if a poet cries?!

while reading these verses, the words of praise of the national poet of Uzbekistan, Muhammad Yusuf, "Poets are the ambassadors of goodness" will flash in your heart. Indeed, poets are singers of the soul, interpreters of the heart. Not everyone is lucky enough to be able to pick up cute words from the bountiful of words. Poets live by missing the unmissable. Even if he cries his heart out and makes his heart sad, he lives with his destiny. In fact, poets are pure people who do not wish any harm to others. The artist's heart, amazed by the sufferings and joys of the world, overflows with words and writes on fire. Word magicians want their writings to reach the hearts of the poets like blessings. Poets perceive the world with the eyes of the heart. And with words, it is a balm for sick hearts. It is known that the themes of mother, Motherland, and love are immortal themes in poetry. In the work of Mirzohid Botirov, the theme of love is also celebrated in a special spirit.

Having an attack of nostalgia,
I could not press my lungs.
Dear Mirza,
Lost to the springs,
Oh my real world
One less for a lover?!
If I look for your face in the moon,
The cloud cover kept the secret.
who veiled the cloud,
If I touch your lips.
Lailatul Qadr Day,
God sent me
Angels in your name,
He whispered..

It seems that the clarity and sincerity in the image of feelings are prominent in the beautiful verses dedicated to the longing for the unrequited love. Each poem of the poet requires a special study. One of the most important topics in the poet's poetry is his writings about mother, life, philosophy of life, envy, a pitiable vice in human character. The royal theme of the artist's poetry is made up of dreamy, unique verses dedicated to the mother:

My grief always leads
I'm going to you
Tell me if I'm a balm
Ilvirak to your soul?!
Built by swallows,
Sabil to your porch,
My heart came with a hug

I can't fit, Mom!

It is understood that these writings are dedicated to a mother whose love is immeasurable on earth, and who, in our ways of life, in achieving great achievements, if we are ill, not herself, but her child, who holds dear liver from her soul. When you read it, you will feel the poet's pain, and you will understand the pain of the heart that misses its heavenly flower mother. The second aspect is that with this poem, the poet is glorifying the idea that one should appreciate his mother while she is still alive, that it is our duty to honor them. Or again, in his poems on the theme of love, the poet describes the image of a true lover:

Nights stay in my eyes,
The nights are dark in your eyes.
Night falls in my soul,
The days when God did not look,
Days without hearing from you...

DISCUSSION

In our classical literature, the dawn is associated with the symbol of the morning, and the separation is associated with the symbol of the night. In other words, life for a lover begins at night, because the soul, which is in a state of separation and emigration, prefers to live at night with the memories of a friend. Observing the work of the poet, it is not difficult to notice the primacy of a special philosophical spirit in his poems. His following verses also confirm how correct our opinion is:

We have gone through something,
He is not satisfied with the past.
He embraces happiness with his hands,
Desire never dies

Or:

The heart pulled back today,
Doomsday is imminent.
Happiness itself does not know,
Forgive the unfortunate, my God!

In his poem, the poet seems to remind that a peaceful and calm day is a happiness in itself, that you should live with gratitude for every passing moment and second. In the end, he asks God to forgive those ignorant people who did not live thankfully, who lived their lives lightly and in a way of enjoying themselves, and those who did not feel the happiness of being born in this country. From one point of view, these scriptures contain the spirit of urging people to learn from every moment of life and exemplary events and to live a good life. While walking in Mirzohid Botirov's gulshan, we see many poetic masterpieces rich in allusions and expressions. One of such poems is the poem "A Ship Without a Sail". In this poem, the poet compares life to a ship without a sail:

My friends, I'm old enough to live,
I am happy or unhappy world?
Shaking the flow,
goes away
A ship without a sail called life!

If the poem means that we should feel that whether a person is happy or unhappy, life passes, and life is fleeting even in seconds, if we take a deeper approach, we can call this poem an invitation not to waste life. Because, with attention to the main essence, this meaning is understood in the context of the topic. That is, you will once again understand that how to spend the life measured by God (a ship without a sail) is up to a person. In another poem, Mirzohid Botirov calls people to purity and purity through the detail of rain, which involuntarily makes hearts tremble:

of this world
half risk
half a dream
Half the grief is real.
it's raining
Look, in the sky,
The prayer season has begun!

I would not exaggerate if I say that these verses are an example of the naturalness of the poet's poetry. Studying the researched verses shows that at first, it is natural for a self-realized person to look at the rain falling from the sky and ask him to forgive me for all my sins. Only when a person prays does his soul rest. The sadness and worries that crushed his heart recede. He becomes a virtuous person. The poet, who wants the rain to wash away all the pains and sorrows of people with prayer, skilfully infuses life philosophy into the layers of verses. When I observe the poet's poetry, when I study the verses about envy, a negative vice in human character, the artist's skill in depicting the reality of life is clearly visible.

One day I'm happy, one day we're short,
What I write is an ointment for the world,
Don't let sadness lurk in my tracks,
The green garden of the envious.
I feel sorry for myself,
What can I do to you if I live?
The pen does not fall from my hands,
The garden of the envious, says the artist.

The word "jealousy" is shown in the dictionary to mean "Archish", "Envy". It seems that if a person is jealous of someone, this is a sin, and its burden will tear the soul. From this it can be concluded that a person should never live with envy, it is emphasized that he should live with lust. The poet explained that a jealous person can never achieve high results. This example of the poet's work reminds once again that envy is the biggest obstacle for a person who aspires to bright destinations and urges to be aware of envious people.

The image of a proud person is also reflected in Mirzohid Botirov's poetry. Proud people remain proud, no matter how many contradictions there are during their lives, they absorb all pain and sorrow. Although there were several times of severe trials during his life, he always laughed and got over it:

This is the world
passing caravan,
If you are lucky, sometimes you don't need it.
The root is food for worms,
Standing dying trees!!

Pride in human character has always been the main motto of pious souls. Therefore, proud people have achieved their goal. Their support is the Truth alone!! There is no savior but the truth. There is another tradition in the poet's poetry, the poem "Letter to God" can be cited as a vivid example of praise and praise to God, which is present in the works of great representatives of Uzbek classical literature.

In my wishes,
In my dreams, in my prayers,
in the breadth of my heart,
My feelings are beautiful with you!

Or

Give me peace
only to my heart,
Let your love flow.
I feel you
I'm asking you
You are the one I lean on, the one I try,
Patience flowers!!

CONCLUSION

A person asks only God in his lonely moments for the answer to the brightest wishes in his heart. The poet wants to live with the love of the truth for a lifetime, and that divine love will give him hope and patience. Actually, if we pay attention to the essence of the question of who can write a letter to God, we can understand that only a conscious person who knows himself can write it. In general, this type of soul, burdened by the sufferings and worries of life, does not write the lamentation of the heart to God, and even when writing it, it overflows. Of course, it can be seen that there are other poems related to the theme of love for God, the deity in the poet's poetry. The main reason why Mirzohid Botirov's poems quickly reach the heart is the preservation of the people's spirit in the poems, the clarity of the images and the special sincerity. It should be said that during the study of the poet's work, you will witness the wide range of topics, and analyzing other poems and researching their specific aspects is one of the most important tasks.

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